

Advancing the methods of ethics: is triangulation an option?

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Abstract

This working paper addresses the instrumentalisation of ethics, particularly in the context of artificial intelligence, where ethical debates have been accused of becoming superficial public relations exercises. The paper argues that the current trends of “ethicswashing” and “ethics bashing” are undermining the rigour and credibility of ethical inquiry. To tackle this crisis this paper proposes to make use of triangulation. This methodology would require researchers to carry out at least three ethical inquiries – each grounded in a different ethical theory. Because of its multi-perspective and theory-based approach, triangulation could provide ethics the currently missing rigour. The paper is divided into two sections: the *pars destruens*, which critiques the current state of ethics, particularly in AI, and the *pars construens*, which offers a methodological foundation for a more robust ethical inquiry. The first section highlights the trivialization of ethics, portraying the dire situation with a focus on AI ethics. The second section proposes rebuilding ethical methodology through clear definitions and the introduction triangulation. This methodology is inspired by the successful practice of theory triangulation in other fields and aims to counteract fast-paced and shallow ethical assessments with more meaningful, less biased, and less instrumentalizable research. By adopting triangulation, the paper aims to safeguard the discipline of ethics from becoming a mere tool for justifying behaviours and to ensure it remains a rigorous, credible, and analytically clear field of inquiry.

Keywords: ethicswashing, ethics bashing, methods, theory triangulation, social sciences, rigour

Introduction

In this article, we build on Marks's (Marks, 1991) observation of the widespread instrumentalisation of ethics, trivialising the numerous philosophical debates. We argue that the situation has not improved but worsened (Schultz et al., 2024). We aim to contribute with a methodological approach to addressing this current challenge of applied ethics, inside and outside academia.

Among the practical philosophy discussions, the most striking case that depicts the fogging of the ethical inquiry (and of ethics in general) is that around artificial intelligence. This ethical debate, which accelerated after the response of the tech industry and legislators to the recent “techlash” (E. Smith, 2018), has been accused, among others, of “ethicswashing” (Metzinger, 2019) and “ethics bashing” (Bietti, 2020). These two harsh (and worrying) accusations allege that the need for fast, ready-made ethical compliance structures has caused the trivialisation and instrumentalisation of ethics and turned the ethical inquiry into a communicative façade and a public relations exercise aimed at “creating the surface illusion of positive change without the veritable reality” (Obradovich et al., 2019). This proliferation of (allegedly) ethical inquiries and ethical principles is also creating “a supermarket of principles and values, where private and public actors may shop for the kind of ethics that is best retrofitted to justify their behaviours, rather than revising their behaviours to make them consistent with a socially accepted ethical framework” (Floridi, 2019). As such, the co-optation of ethics is jeopardising the discipline's rigour, credibility, and analytical clarity. Most fundamentally, it questions ethics' existence.

The situation is dire: “ethics is under siege” (Bietti, 2020). To safeguard the discipline, a rigourisation of the ethical debate is necessary. In this paper, we offer a first step in this direction by transposing the notion of theory triangulation – a practice with decades of literature documenting its success – to ethics. This new methodology is a process by which an ethical judgement – be it normative or evaluative – is the result of a triangulation of (at least) three other ethical judgments grounded in different ethical theories. This triangulated structure has as its constitutive aim that of countering the current fast-paced, ready-made, shallow, trivial, instrumentalised ethical inquiry with a rigorous multi-perspective, theory-based, slow-paced approach that produces a more meaningful, solid, less biased, and less instrumentalisable ethical research.

To defend this shift and to ease the reading, we structured the paper into two sections: a *pars destruens* and a *pars construens*. In the first, we portray the grim picture of what ethics and ethical inquiry are becoming. To present their bleak condition, we decided to focus on the AI ethics debate, as it is one of the fastest-growing discussions and where issues are visible the most. In the second section, we propose to rebuild ethics' methodological foundations on a stronger footing. To this goal, in the first part, we provide a stipulative definition of what we mean by morals, morality, and ethics. These distinctions help us to arrive at our first – and only apparently tautological – finding: ethical debates are about ethics and should be carried out according to the standards set by the ethical inquiry. Based on these points, we then move on to propose what makes a proper ethical judgement. In a second moment, aware that even proper ethical judgments phrased according to the suggested structure could still be instrumentalised to favour one's interest, we introduce the triangulation methodology. We explain triangulation by tracing its original application in the maritime environment and highlighting its fruitful transposition to the social sciences. We then identify the different types of triangulations and propose the adoption of theory triangulation in the ethics field. Conscious that our methodology could raise some objections, we counter some possible objections.

I

Ethics has become a buzzword in many fields. For example, in business, the need for behaviours in accordance with social norms gave rise in the Sixties and Seventies to the field of business ethics (Mees, 2019), which, ever since, has become mainstream. However, few philosophers contribute to the business ethics debate or attend such conferences: an exclusion of philosophers from philosophical discussions (Seele, 2016) – also evident from the fact that academic courses are oftentimes taught not by “experts in ethics” (Klein, 1988), namely those scholars that hold a PhD in philosophy, but by anyone else outside the “religious or philosophy department” that can offer real “guidance on [the] ethical interpretation of real life issues” (McDonald & Donleavy, 1995).

Nevertheless, the poster child of what could be coined as an ‘ethicsdemic’ is the AI field. The AI world has been shaken by a widespread technological backlash (E. Smith, 2018) stemming from the numerous reports documenting all sorts of AI scandals, from racially discriminatory algorithms to crashing self-driving cars (Blauth et al., 2022; Floridi, 2019; Flowerman, 2023; Obermeyer et al., 2019; Truby, 2020). This “techlash” (E. Smith, 2018) has led to a general questioning of the AI sector’s legitimacy and ethicality (Bryson, 2020; Martin & Waldman, 2022; Wischmeyer & Rademacher, 2020), an issue addressed by the industry and governments through the establishment of *ethical* guidelines, the set-up of *ethical* standards, the listing of *ethical* principles, or the creation of *ad hoc ethical* boards (Bietti, 2020; Hao, 2019).

Although these efforts have been praised as the first step in the right direction (Floridi, 2019; Leufer & Hidvegi, 2019), criticisms have soon been raised. Allegedly, the growing demand for ethical assessments (Sia, 2010), principles, and ethics-related structures has caused an instrumentalisation and trivialisation of the ethical inquiry (Bietti, 2020) and induced an inflation of its content and quality (Seele, 2022). The accusation against the sector – and academia, too (Ochigame, 2019) – is unsparing: “ethicswashing” (Metzinger, 2019). Coined by Thomas Metzinger, a philosopher and member of the European High-Level Expert Group on AI, ethicswashing consists of the instrumentalisation of ethics into a misleading, superficial communication of ethical compliance – not backed by any substantive and concrete action – solely aimed at ameliorating (or securing) one’s corporate image, gaining financial benefits, or avoiding regulations in the sector (Freiman, 2022; Klöver & Fanta, 2019; Metzinger, 2019; Obradovich et al., 2019; Peukert & Kloker, 2020; Schultz et al., 2024).

Hence, ethical debates, in this case around AI, are accused of having become a mere “public relations campaign [aimed at] creating the surface illusion of positive change without the veritable reality” (Obradovich et al., 2019). In practice, ethicswashing covers all sorts of vague or unimplementable ethical guidelines and principles (Hao, 2019; Mittelstadt, 2019; Stix, 2021; Tigard, 2021) touted by firms that adopt ethics as a mere instrument in their toolkit for corporate communication strategies (Bietti, 2020) and because of its lacking of enforceable mechanisms that permit them to continue with their business-as-usual (Hagendorff, 2020; Ressayguier & Rodrigues, 2020).

Nevertheless, such an instrumental use of ethics should not be understood as a mere marketing strategy but as a fundamental ontological shift: ethics is not valued anymore intrinsically (i.e., valued *per se*) but only instrumentally (i.e., on what it produces). In Kantian terms, we could say that ethics has become a mere means to an end and is no longer an end in itself. This ontological demotion has epistemological repercussions: the slow, “aspirational” ethical inquiry that “takes moral principles seriously in achieving better knowledge and understanding of a state of affairs or phenomenon” (Bietti, 2020) has been turned into a mere value-dependent, fast-paced, results-seeking practice necessary to obtain reputational or financial profits: an “ethics theatre” (Parson et al., 2019). As such, to keep up the rhythm dictated by the demand, the ethical inquiry has been trivialised into “deceptively simple” (Madaio et al., 2020), ready-made, yes/no compliance check forms like those used by pilots before take-off (Cramer et al., 2019; Duncan & Whittington, 2014; Holstein et al., 2019; Madaio et al., 2020), which cannot provide the shadows and complexities inherent to ethical dilemmas and whose deliverables are doubtful to society (Bietti, 2020).

The overall picture is dire. A new conception of ethics and the ethical inquiry are necessary.

II

Having concluded our *pars destruens* that exposed ethics' alarming state of affairs, we move to our *pars construens*, which aims to put the ethical inquiry on more secure footings. In this section, we provide a stipulative definition of ethics, morals and morality. We then propose triangulation as a solution to the above-mentioned ethics crisis.

1. *Ethical debates are about ethics*

In the academic literature, there is an ongoing debate over whether ethics and morality are the same concept or not, and whether one includes the other (Darwall, 2017; Harper, 2009; Williams, 1986). In contrast to those who hold that ethics and morality are the same and that the ontological distinction between them is unnecessary and only creates confusion (Garnett, 1951; Harper, 2009), we align with those who advocate that ethics is not morality (Frankena, 1974; Lee, 1928; Weiss, 1942; Wienpahl, 1948) and, as such, that the two should be distinguished (Darwall, 2017). Although, to some, this clarification may appear trivial, we believe it to be paramount since the everyday language uses ethics as a synonym for morality and *vice versa* (an undisciplined use often also found in philosophical texts) might represent the first source of the conflation between moral judgements and ethical ones and a crucial element of the current ethics inflation. Therefore, to avoid linguistic ambiguity, let us present our stipulative definition of morals, morality, and ethics.

We define morals as “the broad field of conduct evaluated in terms of its aims, ends, or results” (Lee, 1928), where we classify positive values as good and negative ones as bad. Its narrower concept is that of morality, which we use to refer to the context-bound, gut-feeling, “socially learned, and apparently self-evident rules of right conduct in any community” (Keniston, 1965); as such, “moral codes vary and ought to vary from place to place and time to time” (Weiss, 1942). Hence, moralities are standardised complexes of conduct evaluation that imply a reference according to which the group member is sanctioned or praised. In simpler terms, moralities define whether an action *A* infringes or not the moral system *S*. Examples of morality are the Confucian or the Christian ones: as such, a Christian will be sanctioned if he infringes (by engaging in *A*) or does not abide by

the prescribed principles that make up the Christian morality system *S* (Lee, 1928). To summarise, both concepts relate to one's conduct: the first one in a broad sense, the second in a narrow one.

On the other hand, we delimit ethics to the institutionalised branch of practical philosophy that carries out in a neutral and rational framework a systematised, reason-guided, argument-supported, critical, theoretical, and philosophical reflection *about* conduct (Lee, 1928; Seele, 2022; Sia, 2010). Therefore, ethics is the systematic investigation to rationally evaluate morals (Wienpahl, 1948): “ethics is the genus of which morality is a species” (Darwall, 2017).

These first distinctions permit us a first small step forward in our rigourisation effort since most of the accusations raised against the most different ethical debates can be traced to a conflation between moral statements and ethical judgements: between expressions of gut feelings about a given technology or of conformity with a granted morality, and critical, systematic reflections on the ethicality of such technologies.

As such, we reach our first finding: *any ethical debate should be confined to ethics and the standards imposed by the ethical inquiry*. Although such a conclusion might appear tautological, the currently blurred and fogged conflation between ethics and morality demonstrates that such apparent tautology is more important than ever and these clear distinctions of roles should be re-established.

2. *What makes a proper ethical judgment*

Unsurprisingly, confining ethical debates to ethics does not solve the current instrumentalisation problem, as one could still carry out *ethical* assessments – not moral ones – but in a way that favours one's interests or goals. Hence, the issue moves from an ontological point to an epistemological one on the *mode* of carrying out a proper ethical inquiry to assess the ethicality of a given element *X*. Such an assessment is to be performed through an ethical, systematised, reason-guided, argument-supported, critical, theoretical, philosophical assessment that we define as ‘ethical judgement’ (Alsaad, 2021; Seele, 2022).

This definition of ethical judgment highlights two crucial aspects that should be at the core of any proper ethical inquiry and assessment: transparency and neutrality. Concerning the first, we defend that an ethicist should be as transparent as possible in its terminology. To such end, the use of “theoretical concepts” and “theoretical

words” – instead of “folk ones” (McPherson & Plunkett, 2020), which might be differently interpreted – is highly recommended, and when a term is used in a distinctive manner proper to the ethicist carrying out the analysis, a stipulative definition should be provided. This is because the peculiar and distinctive feature of theoretical concepts is “to provide manifest precision”, which “allow[s] the assessment and transmission of relatively precise theses” (McPherson & Plunkett, 2020). Such requirement does not amount to a mere self-referential cataloguing of terms, “but is truly philosophical” (Lee, 1928) and serves several purposes. First, it avoids ambiguity and permits others to precisely counter the argument not based on presumed understanding but on factual points – thus avoiding “merely verbal disputes” that hinder and ward off the discussion on the ethical analysis (Chalmers, 2011; Jenkins, 2014). Second, it permits to reflect orderly and systematically. Nevertheless, transparency should not be confined to disentangling and settling linguistic ambiguities but should be understood in *sensu latu* and encompass clarity of the argument’s premises, the deduction of the conclusions, and the possible rationale’s shortcomings.

With regards to the second element, namely neutrality, ethicists should be “disinterested in any particular system of morality” (Lee, 1928) – as if it were to favour one over the other, one would “start [the] inquiry with a presumption as to where it is to come out, or even a strong desire and predilection as to where it is to come out” (Lee, 1928): a position that would violate ethics’ *critical* inquiry. Hence, to foster or display its neutrality, the ethicist should also be as transparent as possible in choosing the ethical framework, disclosing the elements that brought one to choose that particular framework over others.

This last point underlines how mere standalone statements – typical of everyday language but oftentimes found in philosophical papers – such as ‘X is unethical’, are senseless. To be meaningful and uphold the features of a proper ethical inquiry, an ethical judgment should be as transparent and neutral as possible. Hence, we propose that meaningful, proper ethical judgements should have something like the following form:

Based on the argument A , built on the premises $P_{1,2,3}$ (where the expressions E, F, G define M, N, O) and grounded in the theory T (chosen because of the reasons $R_{1,2,3}$), X is (un)ethical.

Although much more refined and aligned to the main features of ethics and ethical inquiry, we reckon this definition and structure of an ethical judgment could still be instrumentalised. One could easily think of someone who, for the most diverse reasons, could still rig the system and address the ethical issue at stake by choosing the ethical theory T_x that one reckons might best align with one's interests or expertise. As such, by choosing the most favourable framework, and maybe by retrofitting a reasonable explanation for its choice with a series of reasons $R_{1,2,3}$, one could – according to the framework just presented – still produce a properly-looking ethical judgement, which could potentially be used for policymaking or agenda-setting.

A first possible solution for this hypothetical – and yet highly probable – scenario could be to analyse reasons and prove that these are genuine and rational, but this would most likely create an *ad infinitum* process where one must justify its justifications and then justify the justifications of the justifications. Hence, this possibility does not seem to be viable. Therefore, we propose a new approach: triangulation, i.e., a process by which an ethical judgement must be a triangulation of (at least) three ethical judgments grounded in different ethical theories.

3. *A new approach: triangulating ethical analyses*

Triangulation comes from the maritime context. It was used by navigators and military strategists to locate, through the use of geometry principles, the exact location of an object, be it a boat or a target (Hammersley & Atkinson, 1983; H. W. Smith, 1975).

The process – still used today – runs as follows: you are going out for a day of sailing when the weather conditions quickly worsen. Unfortunately, a violent storm catches you, and a lightning bolt short-circuits all your electronics: you have no working GPS or other technological instruments. As the storm passes, you have no idea where the winds led you and cannot check your position with your electronics. Luckily, you still have your old-fashioned paper map and your trustworthy analogue compass; moreover, the sky is clearing, so you can start to see the coastline. What do you do? You try to triangulate your position: you point the compass towards the distant lighthouse you see on the horizon and draw a line on the map that corresponds to the direction marked by the compass; you then repeat this procedure with at least two other easily identifiable objects to have

three lines on your map – let’s say a big spur and the small fishermen’s village opposite to it. The triangle where all three lines intersect will tell you your position.

The social sciences adopted such a process in the Sixties and Seventies (Blaikie, 1991; UNAIDS, 2010) thanks to the works of Webb et al. (1966). Built on the research of Campbell and Fiske (D. T. Campbell & Fiske, 1959), they aimed at overcoming the “complacent dependence on single operational definitions of theoretical concepts” (Blaikie, 1991). Ever since, the practice has become a widely used methodological strategy (Mathison, 1988). Triangulation in the social sciences is a metaphorical reading of the position-determination process used in the navigational environment. It consists of analysing a given phenomenon under different theoretical and methodological lenses. The use of different points, likewise in the maritime example, increases the accuracy of the final judgment and strengthens the findings (Jick, 1979; Thurmond, 2001) since any evidence would be corroborated (van Drie & Dekker, 2013) “by showing that independent measures of it [two, or ideally more] agree with or, at least, do not contradict it” (Meijer et al., 2002) – thus creating a sort of triangle like the one on the map.

Its application rests on two assumptions. The first one is, as underlined by Blaikie (1991), that “[n]o single method [or theory] is always superior. Each has its own special strengths [,] weaknesses [and biases]”. The second, which directly links to the former, is that, by using multiple approaches, the strengths of each theoretical and methodological lens are “exploited and [... their] liabilities neutralised” (Jick, 1979). Because of these features, triangulation makes for stronger, more valid, and more credible results (Denzin, 1970; Hammersley & Atkinson, 1983, p. 198; Jick, 1979; Thurmond, 2001) that depict a deeper, full-fledged, and comprehensive overall picture (Banik, 1993; UNAIDS, 2010). However, it may happen that crossing multiple methods and theories does not “decrease alternative explanations” (Mitchell, 1986) but actually does the opposite. Nevertheless, such an uncovering of deviancies must not be seen as a weakness of the process but, on the other hand, as an additional strength. In fact, these deviances enrich the epistemic quality of the overall rationale (Banik, 1993; Jick, 1979) by either integrating emerging issues or rejecting them through the development of additional arguments.

Having established the assumptions on which triangulation rests and the advantages it provides, we now move to its main applications in the social sciences. In his seminal work, Denzin (1970) identifies four of them. First,

data triangulation (also known as “triangulation by data source” (Meijer et al., 2002)) consists of using multiple data sources collected in different temporal and geographical settings and by different persons (Meijer et al., 2002; UNAIDS, 2010). Second, *investigator triangulation* (also known as “triangulation by researcher” (Meijer et al., 2002)) makes use of more than one researcher to study a phenomenon with the goal of decreasing any bias inherent to the researchers and increasing credibility through confirmation by the other investigators (Joslin & Muller, 2015). Such a triangulation compares to the interrater reliability of quantitative methods (Meijer et al., 2002). Third, *theory triangulation* (also known as “triangulation by theory” (Meijer et al., 2002)) consists of using multiple theoretical frameworks to interpret results or phenomena (Meijer et al., 2002; UNAIDS, 2010). Fourth, *methodological triangulation* (also known as “triangulation by method”, “multi-method”, or “methods triangulation” (Greene & Caracelli, 1997; Meijer et al., 2002)) consists of conducting a study through the use of multiple methods such as, among others, observations or interviews (Meijer et al., 2002; UNAIDS, 2010). A further internal differentiation of this type of triangulation is between within-method triangulation and across-method triangulation (Joslin & Muller, 2015). To these four types, Miles and Huberman (1994) add a fifth: *triangulation by data type*, which consists of using different types of data (quantitative and qualitative) and combining them (Meijer et al., 2002).

Given (i) the above-defined epistemic nature of the ethical inquiry, namely theory-based, systematised, reason-guided, argument-supported, and critical, and (ii) the previous literature that sketched the transposition of triangulation to philosophy (Joslin & Muller, 2015) and – more specifically – to ethics (Seele, 2022), we decided to apply *theory triangulation* to the ethical inquiry through what we call ‘ethics theory triangulation’.

4. Ethics theory triangulation

Ethics theory triangulation, similar to theory triangulation in the social sciences, would consist of triangulating three separate ethical analyses on a given ethical question – grounded in three different ethical theories – and then assessing their convergence. This methodological proposal could permit to reach a multi-perspective final ethical judgement, much more solid, complex, nuanced, and full-fledged than single ones (Seele, 2022; van Drie & Dekker, 2013) as the inherent issues of each theory could be annulled by the use of other theories. Moreover, due to the necessity of carrying out the ethical inquiry within three diverse ethical theories, such a *modus*

operandi would be less likely to be instrumentalised – since one would have to rig not *one* ethical judgement but at least *three*. Such a difficulty, however, does not exclude *in toto* the possibility of instrumentalisation: it only brings it to a level that one might reasonably consider it difficult enough not to be undertaken to the same level to which it is currently occurring. For all these reasons, we believe that ethics theory triangulation could represent the first needed step in rigourising debates of applied ethics.

5. Countering possible objections

Having presented the functioning of ethics theory triangulation and its benefits in countering the current ethics instrumentalisation and inflation, and in promoting ethics rigourisation, we now move to respond to possible counterarguments to our methodological proposal.

First, it could be retorted to us that the multi-perspective approach we advocate for through our ethics theory triangulation is time-consuming since one must not only carry out three separate ethical inquiries and come up with three ethical judgments but also confront the different results of theirs and analyse possible convergences and divergences (UNAIDS, 2010) to reach a final triangulated ethical judgment. We are perfectly aware of this feature, but we deem that the ethical inquiry cannot be rushed nor transformed into a high-paced reflection without turning into a shallow analysis – as the current ethics inflation demonstrates. Therefore, this first accusation is, *de facto*, a strength of this approach.

A second and more critical charge could be that the ethics theory triangulation naively thinks that theories can be aggregated (Hammersley & Atkinson, 1983): an assumption that does not consider that certain theories are incommensurable. As such, the claim would defend that our proposed approach could work only whenever there are common ontologies (Blaikie, 1991), or – if there were to be incommensurabilities – they would reduce the multiplicity of theories into a single one by analysing the others through the chosen lens (Bednarz, 1985). This contention needs to be tackled on two grounds. First, if there were to be incommensurability between theories that results in a disagreement on the conclusion reached, such incommensurability should not be seen as a hindrance to the process but as a positive aspect since it complexifies the final ethical judgement and departs from the now pursued yes/no, ready-made ones that are plaguing numerous ethical discussions. In addition, it

should be remarked that in our proposal, the final multi-perspective judgement does not aim at bridging theories, nor is it a middle ground – but it only shows convergence or divergence to increase the judgment’s epistemic power and reliability. Second, for the sake of argument, let us assume that what has been argued insofar is not the case, it could still happen that diametrically opposed ethical stances that disagree on foundational points might converge in very *specific* circumstances and on *particular* cases: a “single-issue reconciliation” (I. J. Campbell, 2018). This is the case, for example, in the animal welfare ethical debate, where the alleged irreconcilable divergence between animal welfarism (supported by those who defend an expansion of moral consideration to individual nonhumans, granted the presence of some morally relevant feature (Callicott, 1980)) and ecological ethics (advocated by those that ascribe moral value to ecological communities – instead of individuals – and a differential one to its members (I. J. Campbell, 2018)) can coincide on issues such as species management through therapeutic hunting (Varner, 2002). This response underlines how the contention of incommensurability is not an issue at all, but if considered so, it remains contingent and not an inherent flaw of the proposed practice.

A third point that could be raised against us is that divergencies are not a strength of the proposed approach but a weakness. It could be argued that providing alternatives *decreases* – contrary to what we defended – the epistemic power of the triangulated ethical judgment. We beg to differ. To explain why such nonconformity generated by opposing theories is of fundamental importance and increases the overall epistemic quality, we propose to make an analogy with dissenting or concurring opinions, namely the alternative decisions – typical of certain judicial systems – of judges that oppose (or agree on the conclusions but not on the argumentation of) the majority’s decision (Wex Definitions Team, 2021, 2022). These alternatives do not mine the epistemic power of the majority position, but – on the other hand – they better it by integrating new elements (Galbraith, 1973), which require advocates of the majority opinion to better justify their position (Dooley, 1999), and increasing transparency about the complexity and nuances of the issue (Azizi, 2011). Likewise, having a theoretical approach whose conclusions do not align with the others enriches the epistemic quality of the overall rationale (Banik, 1993; Jick, 1979): it helps integrate new issues or reject them through the introduction of additional arguments, better formulate the contrasting alternatives’ position, and further increases transparency by not concealing opposing perspectives.

Conclusions

The AI ethical debate is the poster child of the dire state in which ethics stands: the need for fast, ready-made ethical compliance structures has allegedly caused its trivialisation and instrumentalisation and turned the ethical inquiry into a communicative façade that is jeopardising the whole discipline's rigour, credibility, and analytical clarity. Such trivialisation is questioning ethics' own existence. To tackle this existential issue, we called for a de-trivialisation of ethics and proposed a first step in this direction by transposing the fruitful practice of triangulation to the realm of ethical inquiries.

To achieve this goal, we started with the stipulative definition of morals as the broad field of conduct and morality as the narrow one. This permitted us to juxtapose them with ethics, which we identified as the systematised, reason-guided, argument-supported, critical, theoretical, philosophical reflection *about* conduct – set up in a neutral and rational framework. Such a contrast underlined our first, apparently tautological, contribution: ethical debates must be confined to the realm of ethics and must be based on ethical inquiries carried out according to the standard of the practice. This distinction should help in a first skim of the debates, eliminating all those moral judgments based on gut feelings that are, nevertheless, touted as ethical ones.

Having defined the boundaries of ethical debates, we then moved to clarify the features of an ethical inquiry and what an ethical judgment should look like. We proposed that they should have a specific form so as to increase transparency and uphold neutrality. Nevertheless, aware that even proper ethical judgments phrased according to the suggested structure could still be instrumentalised to favour one's interest, by choosing the most favourable theoretical framework to achieve one's expected results, we suggested applying the notion of triangulation, i.e., the practice – originally used within the maritime environment to find unknown positions based on the relative position to other objects – of using multiple theories or methods to increase rigour, accuracy and decrease biases and add overall quality to the argument.

To pre-emptively silence oppositions, we tackled what we believe could be three main accusations to our approach. The first charge, which dealt with the additional time required by the multiple steps of the ethics

theory triangulation process, was not disputed but internalised; this is because ethics theory triangulation aims at re-valourising the ethical inquiry from what it has been transformed into. The second contention, which addressed a possible incommensurability among the different theoretical perspectives, was more important but debunked by showing that our approach does not aim to bridge theories but to highlight convergences and divergences so as to strengthen ethical judgments through various corroborations. Moreover, it was also displayed how incommensurable theories might coincide in specific cases. Finally, we tackled the possible argument that having more – and different – perspectives on the same issue might decrease the overall epistemic quality of arguments. We counterargued this point through an analogy with the legal system that displays how having concurrent or dissenting opinions is actually beneficial and upholds neutrality and transparency, the two main tenets of the ethical inquiry.

In conclusion, we believe that ethical inquiries carried out through the ethics theory triangulation would provide a multi-perspective final ethical judgement that is much more rigorous, solid, complex, nuanced, and full-fledged than single-theory ones, and, more importantly – considered today’s ethicswashing and ethics trivialisation phenomena – less likely to be instrumentalised and biased. As such, we reckon that this approach could represent a first step towards de-trivialising ethical debates.

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